

fertilizer was 40 kg N (urea), 17.6 kg P (superphosphate), 33 kg K (potassium chloride), and 3,000 kg CaO (calcium carbonate)/ ha .

Forty-day-old seedlings were planted at 20×20cm spacing in a randomized

complete block design. Plants were scored for Fe toxicity on a 1-9 scale at 4 and 8 wk after transplanting. Grain yield was recorded at maturity.

Varietal differences in tolerance for Fe toxicity were noticed. Fe toxicity was

more severe at 4 wk than at 8 wk after transplanting (Table 2). Addition of P and Ca fertilizers reduced its extent. Local variety Guichao yielded significantly more than any of the test varieties. *ℳ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Experimental mutagenic method for improving rice strains in Vietnam

Phan Phai Tran Duy Quy, Agricultural Genetics Centre, Hanoi, Vietnam

The National Strain Testing Centre (NSTC) of Vietnam has tested two rice mutants. Mutant DB250 is the result of irradiating F₁ dry grains from the cross of TB₁ (a Vietnamese local variety) and IR22 at 25 kR along with 0.02% N-Nitrozo N-dimethylurea as spray for 6 h.

DB250 is 1.35-1.50 m high, has a hard and big culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to 120 kg N/ha. It was

submerged 7-10 d after 4 wk of culture, but mortality was not high. At maximum tillering, submergence for 12 d resulted in 20% mortality, compared with 80% for IR27 and several IRRI strains. DB250 has a 1000-grain weight of 26-27 g and yields 4.5 t/ha over a large area. In NST-C tests in 1980-83 in 14 provinces of the North, DB250 was first among 16 adapted submergence-tolerant rices.

Mutant NN22-98 was obtained in 1973 by treating IR22 grains with 0.02% N-NitroLoethylurea for 18 h (pH 7). It was separated from the M₂ population in 1974.

NN22-98 is 1.2-1.4 m high, has a hard culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to as much as 100 kg N/ha. Its 1,000-grain weight is 29-31 g, compared with the normal 23-25 g. The plant has field resistance to brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2. Mean yield is 4.4-4.6 t/ha. Grain quality is better than that of IR22.

NN22-98 was third among 16 strains of summer rice tested by the NSTC in 1980-83 in 19 provinces of the North. It is still being tested by the Ministry of Agriculture. *ℳ*

Comparison of rice hybrids and local varieties at TNRRRI

M. Subramanian and V. Sivasubramanian, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

Seven rice hybrids from IRRI were tested against three short-duration and five medium-duration Tamil Nadu varieties during 1984 kharif. The trial was laid out in a randomized block with three replications. The 24-d-old seedlings were planted, 1 seedling/hill spaced 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within rows, in 10.35 m² plots and fertilized 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. No plant protection measures were taken, as there was no pest or disease incidence during growth.

Among the hybrids studied, Wei You 64 flowered very early (72 d after seeding [DAS]); IR21895-90-3A/IR54 and IR46830A/IR13292-5-2 flowered late (106 DAS). The remaining hybrids

Performance of rice hybrids and local varieties. TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Hybrid and variety	Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
Wei You 64	72	89.6	4.5
IR46831A/IR54	87	87.5	4.2
IR41828A/Milyang 54	77	81.9	3.7
IR365A/Milyang 54	87	93.7	3.5
97A/Milyang 54	78	97.3	3.1
IR21895-90-3A/IR54	106	123.3	4.0
IR46830A/IR13292-5-2	106	89.4	4.2
IR50 (IR2153-14-1-6-2/IR28//IR36)	76	85.3	4.1
TKM9 (TKM7/IR8)	77	94.9	4.0
ADT36 (Tiruveni/IR20)	79	94.3	4.0
Co 42 (RP-31-49-2/Lab Muey Mahag)	102	124.0	4.2
IR20 (Peta*3/TN1//TKM6)	103	104.4	3.9
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	99	104.4	4.1
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	99	101.4	4.0
White Ponni (AD)	101	152.8	3.9
CD			3.8
CV			9.5

flowered between 77 and 87 DAS (see table).

IR21895-90-3A/IR54 was tallest of the hybrids, and lodged. White Ponni (AD), one of the medium-duration tall check varieties, also lodged. Check Co

42 partly lodged.

Although yield differences among the hybrids and the check varieties were significant, the yield potential of the hybrids was less than 4.5 t/ha. The maximum yield (4.5 t/ha) was registered

by Wei You 64, against 4.03 t/ha registered by early-maturing check variety IR50 and 4.05 t/ha by TKM9.

Of the 2 mediumduration hybrids.

IR46830A/IR13292-5-2 registered the highest yield (4.2 t/ha), on a par with the yield of local check Co 42. Although

the hybrid had a long panicle (av length 29.4 cm), high spikelet sterility (40%) reduced the yield. *J*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Anther culture of Basmati 370 at IRRI. A. Gamma ray-induced green plant regeneration

F.J. Zapata, R.R. Aldemita, L.B. Torrizo, A. U. Novero, S.K. Raina, and R. R. Rola, IRRI

Breeding studies for the improvement of high quality Basmati rice have long been undertaken. So far no variety comparable or superior to Basmati rice has been released.

We conducted experiments on the improvement of the Basmati-type rice through anther culture in the Tissue Culture Facility at IRRI. Gametoclonal variants for plant type and soil constraints can be obtained and consequently fixed when anthers of rice varieties are passed through anther culture. Preliminary studies (Table 1) using different callus induction media showed the predominance of albino plant regeneration. Green plant regeneration was not observed.

To find out if irradiation stress would produce genetic alterations in the cell which would improve callus induction and green plant regeneration. Basmati

Table 1. Anther culture of Basmati 370 in three media.

Media ^a	Callus production (%)	Calli plated (no.)	Albino plant production (no.)
E10	5.71	41	148.78
E10 M	2.56	10	80
E10 T	1.29	6	50

^a E10 consists of Gamborg's B5-basic media with 1 mg 2,4 dichloro-phenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter, 0.5 mg 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)/liter, 0.5 mg indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)/liter, and 5 mg glucose/liter; E10M consists of E10 with 0.002 M 2 [N-morpholine] ethane sulfonic acid; E10T consists of E10 without 2,4-D, but with 1.5 mg 2,4,5 trichlorophenoxy acetic acid/liter.

Percentage of callus induction and albino plant regeneration as affected by gamma irradiation dosage on Basmati 370.

370 seeds were subjected to irradiation dosages of 15, 20, and 25 krad at an application dose rate of 1.2 krad / min from Cobalt 60 gamma cell. Anthers collected from plants of irradiated seeds in the middle uninucleate to early binucleate stages of pollen development were plated in G4 medium (E10 medium without glucose). Calli produced were transferred to a liquid Murashige and Skoog (MS) regeneration medium with 1 mg kinetin/liter, 1 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter, and 20 mg abscisic acid (ABA)/ liter for 4 wk and then to ABA-free semisolid MS regeneration medium.

Callus production percentage and albino plant regeneration (Fig. 1) were lowest at 20 krad. Green plant regeneration was observed only in 20 krad gamma ray (Table 2). These results show that genetic alterations may have been induced by gamma irradiation which decreased callus production efficiency, but lessened albinism, and triggered green plant regeneration. Although irradiation was directed

Table 2. Effect of irradiation on plant regeneration of Basmati 370 in G4 medium.

Irradiation dosage (krad)	Calli plated (no.)	Calli with green plants (%)
0	10	0
15	61	0
20	23	26.1
25	84	0

randomly to the plant cells, genetic alterations manifested were favorable for green plant regeneration.

We are screening regenerated green plants for agronomic characters and yield. *J*

Anther culture of Basmati 370 at IRRI. B. Effect of glucose in anther culture of irradiated Basmati 370

F.J. Zapata, K.K. Aldemita, L.B. Torrizo, A. U. Novero, S. K. Raina, and R. R. Rola, IRRI

Previous report on the anther culture of Basmati 370 showed that applying 20 krad gamma rays to rice seeds triggered green plant regeneration. However, callus production efficiency remained low. To improve callus induction, glucose was added to the medium.

Anthers derived from 20 krad irradiated plants at middle uninucleate to early binucleate stages of pollen development were plated in 2 liquid callus induction media consisting of basic Gamborg's medium with 1 mg 2,4-D/ liter, 0.5 mg indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)/ liter, 0.5 mg 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)/ liter and 5 g glucose/ liter (E10), and without glucose (G4). Calli produced were transferred to a liquid Murashige and Skoog (MS)